

Optimization of cold-formed c-shaped and z-shaped thin-walled profiles

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Abstract:

The paper is devoted to the optimization of thin-walled beam cross-sections subjected to pure bending, with a focus on achieving efficient structural performance through multi-objective optimization. Four non-standard cross-sectional types (C1, C2, Z1, Z2) manufactured by Zaprom Ltd were analyzed at two beam lengths (420 mm and 800 mm). The adopted criteria were the minimization of the cross-sectional area, reflecting material consumption, and the minimization of maximum deflection, indicating structural stiffness. The optimization was conducted using the Normal Constraint method, ensuring a uniform distribution of Pareto-optimal solutions. The results revealed distinct trade-offs between mass and stiffness, with C2 consistently outperforming the other variants by offering the most favorable balance. C1 proved less efficient, while Z1 was found to be the least effective in mass utilization. Z2 provided intermediate performance, superior to Z1 but inferior to C2. These findings highlight C2 as the most advantageous solution for achieving optimal mass–stiffness efficiency in thin-walled beam design.

Keywords: Thin-walled beam; Optimization, Numerical analysis.

1. Introduction

The shape of the cross-section significantly influences the stability and load-carrying capacity of thin-walled profiles. Studies show that different shapes, such as top-hat, channel, and cruciform sections, exhibit varied stability characteristics under compression

The findings from these studies have practical implications for optimizing the design of thin-walled profiles in construction and engineering applications. By understanding the stability behavior, engineers can enhance the performance and safety of these structures.

Hancock [1] reviewed and summarised the major research developments in cold-formed steel structures published during 1999-2001. Davies [2] outlined recent developments in the practical utilisation of cold-formed steel structures. Messac et al. [3] and Messac and Mattson [4] proposed the normal constraint (NC) method for generating a set of evenly spaced solutions on a Pareto frontier – for multiobjective optimization problems. Magnucki [5] presented optimization of an open cross section of the thin walled beam under strength and stability constraints. Magnucki et al. [6] presented optimal design of an open cross section of a cold formed beam with sinusoidally corrugated flanges. Magnucki and Magnucka-Blandzi [7] proposed a variational design of open cross-section thin-walled beams. Magnucka-Blandzi and Magnucki [8] reviewed selected problems of buckling and optimal design of thin-walled beams.

Magnucka-Blandzi [9] described the effective shaping of cold-formed thin-walled channel beams with double-box flanges subjected to pure bending. Lee et al. [10] used a micro Genetic Algorithm to find an optimum cross-section of cold-formed steel beams. Ostwald et al. [11] and Kasperska et al. [12] analysed the problem of optimal design of the beams with selected channel section shapes under bending moment. Ostwald and Rodak [13] presented an analysis of the multicriteria optimal design of cold-formed beams with generalized open shapes under different loads. Stulpinas and Daniunas [14] developed an optimization algorithm for the closed cross-sections of portal frames members. Sun et al. [15] proposed a novel topology optimization method for thin-walled structures with directional straight stiffeners using the material-field series expansion and multifield superposition. Zhang et al. [16] presents a multi-component topology optimization method for thin-walled structures. Liu et al. [17] studied a global optimization approach based on a numerical implementation of the DSM for the objective function of cold-formed steel columns. Vinot et al. [18] described a methodology for optimizing the shape of thin-walled structure with the use of FEM. Magnucki and Paczos [19] presented theoretical shape optimization of cold-formed thin-walled channel beams with drop flanges in pure bending. Pawlak et al. [20] analysed experimentally and numerically the strength and resistance to loss of stability of thin-walled channel columns. Pawlak et al. [21] presented current state of knowledge of imperfections in thin-walled steel profiles with modified cross-sectional shapes. Mahado [22] analyzed the static non-linear behaviour of thin-walled composite beams with initial imperfections. Jasion et al. [23] conducted numerical and experimental analysis of buckling and post-buckling behaviour of selected cold-formed C-beams with modified cross-sections and compared them to a classical one. Chu et al. [24] investigated numerically the local and distortional buckling behaviour of cold-formed steel zed-section beams subjected to uniformly distributed transverse loads.

The objective of this study was to investigate the efficiency of selected thin-walled beam cross-sections through multi-objective optimization. The research aimed at identifying optimal geometrical configurations that minimize two conflicting criteria: the cross-sectional area, representing material usage and structural mass, and the maximum deflection, reflecting the global stiffness of the element. The optimization process was carried out for different cross-section types (manufactured by Zaprom Ltd) and beam lengths, with the intention of assessing their comparative performance and determining the most effective solutions in terms of the mass–stiffness trade-off.

2. Optimization model – scalar and bi-objective optimization

Structural design, which is a process aimed at achieving a specific goal, such as minimal manufacturing cost, is called structural optimization. When designing beams, many constraints related to strength, stiffness, and stability must be taken into account. Therefore, simply selecting a good structure, one that is acceptable given the constraints, can pose a challenge for the designer. Optimization, therefore, enables the selection of not only a good structure but also one that is optimal with respect to the selected criterion or criteria.

If the construction optimization model contains one criterion, we talk about single-criterion or scalar optimization, while if there are several objective functions, we talk about multi-criterion or vector optimization.

This paper presents a two-criteria optimization of beams C1, C2, Z1, and Z2 (Figure 2 - Figure 5) of the length L subjected to pure bending (Figure 1). The optimization criteria were the beam cross-sectional area and its maximum deflection.

Figure 1 Beam loading scheme

Figure 2 Cross section C1

Figure 3 Cross section C2

Figure 4 Cross section Z1

Figure 5 Cross section Z2

The parameters related to the geometry of the beam cross-section were chosen as decision variables:

$$x = [t, h, b, c, d]^T.$$

The objective functions were:

- cross-sectional area of the beam:

$$f_1(x) = A, \quad (1)$$

- maximum beam deflection:

$$f_2(x) = \sqrt{v^2 + w^2}, \quad (2)$$

where v and w are the displacement of the shear center in the vertical and horizontal planes, respectively, and are calculated from the equation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_z & \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_{yz} & -M_y \\ \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_{yz} & \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_y & 0 \\ -M_y & 0 & GJ_s + \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_\omega + 2\beta_{Cz}M_y \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v \\ w \\ \psi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{4}{\pi}M_y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

And

M_y – bending moment,

E – Young's modulus,

G – Kirchoff's modulus,

J_y, J_{yz}, J_z – moments of inertia,

J_ω – warping constant,

J_s – St-Venant torsion constant,

$$\beta_{Cz} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} \left(I_z \int_A y(y^2 + z^2) dA + I_{yz} \int_A z(y^2 + z^2) dA \right) - z_C,$$

z_C – shear center coordinate

The following constraints were present in the optimization model:

- geometric constraints

$$t_{min} \leq t \leq t_{max},$$

$$4t \leq h + t \leq H_{max},$$

$$3t \leq b + t \leq D_{max},$$

and in the case of cross-sections C1 and C2

$$2t \leq c \leq 0,4(h - t),$$

$$t \leq d \leq b - 0,5t,$$

while in the case of cross-sections Z1 and Z2

$$2t \leq c \leq 0,4h,$$

$$t \leq d \leq \max\{\sqrt{2}(b - t), \sqrt{2}(c - t)\},$$

- strength constraint

$$M_y \leq M_{SC},$$

where

$$M_{SC} = \frac{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}{z_{max} J_z - y_{max} J_{yz}} \frac{\sigma_y}{n}$$

and (y_{max}, z_{max}) is the point where the maximum normal stress occurs, σ_y – yield point, n – safety factor,

- global stability constraint

$$M_y \leq M_{GB},$$

where

$$M_{GB} = \frac{M_{kr}}{n_g}$$

$$M_{kr} = \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 E \frac{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}{J_y} \left\{ \beta_{Sz} \pm \sqrt{\beta_{Sz}^2 + \frac{J_y J_\omega}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} \left[1 + \frac{G J_s}{E J_\omega} \left(\frac{L}{\pi}\right)^2 \right]} \right\},$$

n_g – safety factor,

- local and distortional stability constraint

$$M_y \leq M_{LB},$$

where

$$M_{LB} = \frac{M_{kr}}{n_l}$$

and M_{kr} calculated using the finite strip method, n_l – safety factor,.

- maximum beam deflection constraint

$$\delta_{max} \leq \delta_{dop},$$

where δ_{max} is the maximum deflection of the beam (2), while δ_{dop} is the permissible beam deflection.

3. Results of cross-section optimization

Numerical calculations were performed for the following input data:

- beam length: $L = 420; 800$ mm,
- bending moment: $M_y = 0,2$ kNm
- minimum and maximum dimensions:

dimension	minimum value mm	maximum value mm
t	0,0	1,5
$H = h + t$	0,0	80 for cross-sections C1, C2 120 for cross-sections Z1, Z2
$D = b + t$	0,0	40

- material constants:
 - Young's modulus - $E = 2,0 \cdot 10^5$ MPa,
 - Kirchoff's modulus - $G = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} = 7,6923 \cdot 10^4$ MPa,
 - Poisson's ratio - $\nu = 0,3$,
 - yield point - $\sigma_y = 330$ MPa
- permissible beam deflection - $\delta_{dop} = \frac{L}{250}$
- safety factors:
 - strength $n = 1,5$,
 - global $n_g = 2,7$,
 - local $n_l = 1,8$.

The calculations generated a discrete set of Pareto-optimal and non-dominated solutions, which are presented in the tables and figures. The calculations were performed using the normal constraints method proposed by Messac et al. [3], Messac and Mattson [4]. This method involves optimizing a single objective function with additional constraints. It allows for obtaining all non-dominated solutions, and the resulting discrete set of non-dominated solutions is uniformly distributed on the Pareto boundary. For the problem considered in this study, a single objective function was optimized with an additional constraint dependent on parameter

w . For $w=0,0$, the minimum beam cross-sectional area was obtained, while for $w=1,0$, the minimum beam deflection was obtained.

3.1. Cross-sections C1

Table 1 and Table 2 present the results obtained for C1 beams with lengths $L=420\text{mm}$ and $L=800\text{mm}$, respectively. Figure 6 shows the Pareto-optimal boundaries in the criteria space. The selected optimal cross-sections are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Table 1 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section C1, $M_y = 0.2 \text{ kNm}$, $L = 420 \text{ mm}$

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	77,8	1,114	0,445	49,17	39,55	14,02	5,73
0,1	87,2	0,954	0,444	69,09	39,56	14,64	5,77
0,2	100,9	0,804	0,483	73,70	39,51	17,76	5,82
0,3	119,1	0,665	0,534	78,13	39,45	21,78	5,77
0,4	144,2	0,542	0,603	79,31	39,39	27,94	5,64
0,5	177,9	0,440	0,749	79,25	39,25	28,60	4,09
0,6	219,9	0,357	0,920	79,08	39,08	30,52	2,70
0,7	269,9	0,293	1,141	78,86	38,86	31,09	1,14
0,8	337,3	0,271	1,083	78,92	38,92	31,13	38,37
0,9	393,2	0,221	1,500	78,50	38,50	30,80	14,83
1,0	462,0	0,202	1,500	78,50	38,50	30,80	37,75

Table 2 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section C1, $M_y = 0.2 \text{ kNm}$, $L = 800 \text{ mm}$

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	93,0	3,200	0,458	66,67	39,54	17,60	6,53
0,1	104,4	2,783	0,478	79,01	39,52	19,09	6,44
0,2	119,9	2,394	0,531	78,53	39,45	22,38	6,29
0,3	139,8	2,033	0,588	79,41	39,41	26,91	6,14
0,4	165,7	1,712	0,692	79,29	39,31	28,76	4,74
0,5	198,0	1,435	0,828	79,17	39,17	29,94	3,45
0,6	237,2	1,203	0,992	79,01	39,01	31,12	2,12
0,7	283,1	1,017	1,197	78,80	38,80	31,04	1,20
0,8	347,6	0,955	1,117	78,88	38,88	31,11	38,32
0,9	403,0	0,831	1,302	78,70	38,70	30,96	38,05
1,0	462,0	0,733	1,500	78,50	38,50	30,80	37,75

Figure 6 Pareto-optimal edges for beams with a CI cross-section

$w = 0,0$
 $t = 0,445 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 49,17 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 39,56 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 14,02 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 5,73 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,1$
 $t = 0,444 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 69,09 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 39,56 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 14,64 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 5,77 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,5$
 $t = 0,749 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 79,25 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 39,25 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 28,60 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 4,90 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,9$
 $t = 1,500 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 78,50 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 38,50 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 30,80 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 14,83 \text{ mm}$

$w = 1,0$
 $t = 1,500 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 78,50 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 38,50 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 30,80 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 37,75 \text{ mm}$

Figure 7 Optimal cross-sections C1 for $L = 420 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,0$
 $t = 0,458 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 66,67 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 39,54 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 17,60 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 6,53 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,1$
 $t = 0,478 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 79,01 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 39,52 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 19,09 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,5$
 $t = 0,828 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 79,17 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 39,17 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 29,94 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 3,45 \text{ mm}$

$w = 0,9$
 $t = 1,302 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 78,70 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 38,70 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 30,96 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 38,05 \text{ mm}$

$w = 1,0$
 $t = 1,500 \text{ mm}$
 $h = 78,50 \text{ mm}$
 $b = 38,50 \text{ mm}$
 $c = 30,80 \text{ mm}$
 $d = 37,75 \text{ mm}$

Figure 8 Optimal cross-sections C1 for $L = 800 \text{ mm}$

For cross-section C1, the Pareto front reveals a distinct trade-off between minimizing the cross-sectional area and minimizing maximum deflection. At a beam length of $L=420$ mm, the objective function values range from $A=77,8$ mm²; deflection =1,114 mm (for $w=0,0$) to $A=462,0$ mm²; deflection =0,202mm (for $w=1,0$). A similar pattern is observed for $L=800$ mm, where deflections are approximately three times higher. The most favorable compromise is obtained for weights $w \in [0,4;0,6]$. Within this range, deflection can be reduced by about 50% compared to the minimum-area solution, with only an 80–100% increase in area. It is also noteworthy that geometric parameters h and b frequently reach their upper limits, while dimension d approaches the minimum in certain cases, which may generate technological problems.

3.2. Cross-sections C2

Table 3 and Table 4 present the results obtained for C2 beams with lengths $L=420$ mm and $L=800$ mm, respectively. Figure 9 shows the Pareto-optimal boundaries in the criteria space.

Table 3 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section C2, $M_y = 0.2$ kNm, $L = 420$ mm

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	50,6	0,863	0,477	57,41	15,78	3,19	4,61
0,1	53,2	0,703	0,504	64,51	13,82	3,56	2,22
0,2	57,8	0,547	0,481	68,72	13,59	4,39	6,61
0,3	63,7	0,394	0,496	78,86	12,06	4,22	7,44
0,4	79,3	0,261	0,440	79,46	30,31	4,58	14,45
0,5	115,4	0,168	0,541	79,46	39,46	3,64	22,88
0,6	169,4	0,112	0,613	79,39	39,39	26,45	25,97
0,7	233,1	0,074	0,749	79,25	38,60	31,40	38,22
0,8	306,6	0,057	0,982	79,02	39,02	31,21	38,53
0,9	383,4	0,046	1,236	78,76	38,76	31,01	38,14
1,0	462,0	0,038	1,500	78,50	38,50	30,80	37,75

Table 4 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section C2, $M_y = 0.2$ kNm, $L = 800$ mm

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	65,3	1,488	0,473	72,61	22,54	3,28	6,11
0,1	68,6	1,230	0,483	79,45	20,78	4,32	5,07
0,2	76,9	0,988	0,439	79,54	27,38	4,21	15,08
0,3	92,6	0,772	0,453	79,55	39,55	4,52	17,16
0,4	118,9	0,591	0,553	79,45	39,45	3,63	23,76
0,5	155,1	0,445	0,666	79,33	39,33	3,73	32,75
0,6	199,9	0,327	0,698	79,30	32,34	31,44	31,99
0,7	255,4	0,246	0,815	79,19	39,18	31,35	38,78

0,8	320,5	0,197	1,028	78,97	38,97	31,18	38,46
0,9	389,8	0,164	1,258	78,74	38,74	30,99	38,11
1,0	462,0	0,139	1,500	78,50	38,50	30,80	37,75

Figure 9 Pareto-optimal edges for beams with a C2 cross-section

Cross-section C2 demonstrates the highest efficiency among the investigated variants. For $L=420\text{mm}$, the objective functions vary from $A=50,6\text{mm}^2$; deflection $=0,863\text{ mm}$ to $A=462,0\text{ mm}^2$; deflection $=0,038\text{ mm}$. In comparison to C1, for the same stiffness level, C2 requires a smaller cross-sectional area, highlighting its structural advantage. The “knee” of the Pareto front is located at weights $w \in [0,3;0,5]$. For instance, at $w=0,4$, the solution yields $A=79,3\text{mm}^2$ and deflection $=0,261\text{ mm}$, representing a threefold improvement in stiffness over C1 at a nearly identical area. The results for $L=800\text{ mm}$ show analogous relationships, with deflection values scaling proportionally to beam length.

3.3. Cross-sections Z1

Table 5 and Table 6 present the results obtained for beams with cross-section Z1 and length $L=420\text{mm}$ and $L=800\text{mm}$, respectively. Figure 10 shows the Pareto-optimal edges in the criteria space. The selected optimal cross-sections for the beam with length $L=420\text{mm}$ are presented in Figure 11.

Table 5 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section Z1, $M_y = 0.2\text{ kNm}$, $L = 420\text{ mm}$

w	$f_{1,min}$	$f_{2,min}$	t	h	b	c	d
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	mm ²	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm
0,0	182,5	1,270	1,075	118,93	38,93	47,57	6,02
0,1	192,7	1,132	0,922	119,08	39,08	47,63	25,42
0,2	209,7	1,023	0,980	119,02	39,02	47,61	28,00
0,3	228,1	0,919	1,039	118,96	38,96	47,58	30,82
0,4	247,9	0,821	1,099	118,90	38,90	47,56	33,85
0,5	269,1	0,729	1,160	118,84	38,84	47,54	37,11
0,6	291,6	0,642	1,221	118,77	38,78	47,51	40,58
0,7	315,1	0,560	1,279	118,72	38,72	47,49	44,46
0,8	340,3	0,484	1,339	118,66	38,66	47,46	48,38
0,9	366,5	0,413	1,395	118,60	38,61	47,44	52,80
1,0	398,8	0,368	1,500	118,50	38,50	47,40	54,45

Table 6 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section ZI, $M_y = 0.2 \text{ kNm}$, $L = 800 \text{ mm}$

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	235,4	3,200	1,062	118,94	38,94	47,58	31,93
0,1	248,3	2,974	1,101	118,90	38,90	47,56	33,89
0,2	261,8	2,756	1,140	118,86	38,86	47,54	35,97
0,3	276,0	2,544	1,180	118,82	38,82	47,53	38,16
0,4	290,8	2,340	1,220	118,77	38,78	47,51	40,46
0,5	306,3	2,143	1,259	118,74	38,74	47,50	42,89
0,6	322,3	1,953	1,298	118,70	38,70	47,48	45,46
0,7	339,1	1,771	1,337	118,66	38,66	47,46	48,16
0,8	356,3	1,595	1,373	118,62	38,63	47,45	51,11
0,9	374,4	1,429	1,411	118,58	38,59	47,43	54,12
1,0	398,8	1,334	1,500	118,50	38,50	47,40	54,45

Figure 10 Pareto-optimal edges for beams with a ZI cross-section

Figure 11 Optimal cross-sections Z1 for $L = 420$ mm

For cross-section Z1, the obtained solutions exhibit significantly larger cross-sectional areas for comparable deflections relative to C-type sections. At $L=420$ mm, values range from $A=182,5$ mm²; deflection = 1,270 mm to $A=398,8$ mm²; deflection = 0,368 mm. A similar trend is observed at $L=800$ mm, where deflections increase substantially. The Pareto front has a less favorable shape compared to C-sections, and compromise points within $w \in [0,4;0,6]$ result in relatively high self-weight with only moderate deflection reduction. Consequently, cross-section Z1 should be regarded as less mass-efficient and justifiable primarily in cases dictated by specific geometric or technological constraints.

3.4. Cross-sections Z2

Table 7 and Table 8 present the results obtained for beams with cross-section Z2 and lengths $L=420$ mm and $L=800$ mm, respectively. Figure 12 shows the Pareto-optimal edges in the criteria space. The selected optimal cross-sections for the beam with length $L=420$ mm are shown in Figure 13.

Table 7 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section Z2, $M_y = 0.2$ kNm, $L = 420$ mm

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	95,3	0,989	0,506	68,11	39,49	27,24	6,98
0,1	107,8	0,854	0,535	77,56	39,44	30,92	7,08
0,2	123,5	0,725	0,568	89,16	39,41	35,56	7,09
0,3	143,9	0,605	0,605	103,72	39,38	41,38	7,07
0,4	170,8	0,496	0,659	119,34	39,34	47,74	6,80
0,5	207,8	0,407	0,816	119,18	39,18	47,67	4,80
0,6	253,9	0,334	1,060	113,94	38,94	45,55	1,11
0,7	307,9	0,276	1,250	118,75	38,75	47,50	1,25
0,8	385,5	0,262	1,098	118,90	38,90	47,56	53,46
0,9	450,0	0,224	1,500	118,50	38,50	47,40	28,54
1,0	521,3	0,198	1,500	118,50	38,50	47,40	52,33

Table 8 Set of Pareto-optimal solutions for cross-section Z2, $M_y = 0.2 \text{ kNm}$, $L = 800 \text{ mm}$

w	$f_{1,min}$ mm ²	$f_{2,min}$ mm	t mm	h mm	b mm	c mm	d mm
0,0	104,5	3,200	0,517	77,03	39,48	30,81	7,56
0,1	117,7	2,782	0,549	85,97	39,45	34,36	7,58
0,2	134,2	2,384	0,583	97,10	39,42	38,84	7,60
0,3	155,3	2,015	0,622	111,41	39,36	44,46	7,69
0,4	183,0	1,683	0,708	119,29	39,29	47,72	6,51
0,5	221,8	1,417	1,010	99,48	38,99	39,79	1,12
0,6	262,9	1,166	1,075	117,51	38,92	47,00	1,11
0,7	315,2	0,981	1,280	118,72	38,72	47,49	1,28
0,8	391,5	0,938	1,115	118,88	38,88	47,55	53,41
0,9	453,3	0,811	1,500	118,50	38,50	47,40	29,67
1,0	521,3	0,719	1,500	118,50	38,50	47,40	52,33

Figure 12 Pareto-optimal edges for beams with a Z2 cross-section

Figure 13 Optimal cross-sections Z2 for $L = 420$ mm

Cross-section Z2 occupies an intermediate position between the C-type variants and Z1. For $L=420$ mm, solutions range from $A=95,3$ mm²; deflection =0.989 mm to $A=521,3$ mm²; deflection =0,198 mm. Initial solutions are less favorable than C2 and somewhat heavier than C1 at similar stiffness levels, while at high stiffness the area grows sharply. The most rational compromise occurs within $w \in [0,3;0,5]$, where deflection can be reduced by approximately 50% at the cost of a moderate increase in area. At $L=800$ mm, the same tendencies are observed, with deflections significantly amplified by beam length. In comparative terms, Z2 is less efficient than C2 but superior to Z1, making it a viable alternative when Z-type cross-sections are required.

The comparative analysis of all four cross-sections highlights clear differences in structural efficiency. C2 consistently outperforms the other variants, achieving the lowest deflections for a given cross-sectional area. In practical terms, C2 offers the most advantageous mass–stiffness balance, particularly around the Pareto “knee” ($w \approx 0,3-0,5$), where a significant reduction in deflection is obtained with only a modest increase in area.

C1, while structurally similar, is consistently less efficient than C2 and should be regarded as a secondary option, unless specific design constraints prevent the application of C2. Z1 proves to be the least efficient solution, as it requires markedly larger cross-sectional areas to achieve comparable stiffness. Its application may be justified only in special cases where geometry or

manufacturing constraints necessitate Z-type sections. Z2 represents a middle ground, more effective than Z1 but not as efficient as C2. It is therefore best suited as an alternative when Z-type cross-sections are required by design. Overall, the results indicate that C2 is the optimal cross-section for minimizing both mass and deflection, especially for moderate stiffness requirements. Nevertheless, the final choice should also account for manufacturing feasibility, particularly regarding dimensions approaching limiting values.

4. Conclusions

The conducted research provides comprehensive insight into the optimization of thin-walled beam cross-sections under pure bending conditions. By employing a bi-objective optimization framework, the study systematically evaluated the balance between cross-sectional area and maximum deflection, thereby quantifying the trade-off between material efficiency and structural stiffness. The application of the Normal Constraint method proved effective in generating a well-distributed set of Pareto-optimal solutions, which facilitated a detailed comparative analysis across the four investigated non-standard cross-section types, manufactured by Zaprom Ltd.

The results clearly demonstrate that cross-section C2 consistently exhibits superior performance. For both beam lengths considered, C2 achieved the lowest deflections for a given cross-sectional area. Its Pareto front displayed a distinct “knee” in the region $w \in [0.3; 0.5]$, representing highly favorable compromise solutions. In these cases, substantial reductions in deflection could be obtained with only moderate increases in cross-sectional area. This makes C2 the most efficient option when both material consumption and stiffness requirements are considered simultaneously.

Cross-section C1, while structurally similar to C2, proved consistently less efficient. Although it provides feasible solutions within the investigated range, the corresponding Pareto front indicates that C1 requires noticeably larger areas to achieve the same stiffness as C2. Consequently, C1 should be regarded as a secondary alternative, particularly in situations where design or manufacturing constraints limit the applicability of C2.

Cross-section Z1 emerged as the least effective solution among the analyzed variants. The results showed that Z1 consistently required much larger cross-sectional areas to reach comparable stiffness levels, which translates into significant increases in material usage. This poor mass efficiency makes Z1 a suboptimal choice in most practical applications. Its use could only be justified under specific circumstances, such as geometric or technological requirements that necessitate Z-type geometries.

Cross-section Z2 offered intermediate performance, falling between C1/C2 and Z1. While less efficient than C2, Z2 demonstrated better results than Z1, particularly at moderate stiffness levels. Its Pareto front also revealed acceptable compromise solutions in the range $w \in [0.3; 0.5]$, where meaningful deflection reductions could be achieved without excessive increases in cross-sectional area. Thus, Z2 can be considered a viable alternative when Z-type cross-sections are required by design, even though it cannot match the efficiency of C2.

A consistent observation across all cross-sections was the strong dependence of deflection on beam length. When the length increased from 420 mm to 800 mm, maximum deflections approximately tripled, while the cross-sectional areas required to maintain comparable stiffness

grew significantly. This finding underscores the importance of length as a governing factor in thin-walled beam optimization and highlights the need to account for scaling effects in practical design.

In conclusion, the comparative analysis unambiguously identifies C2 as the optimal cross-section, delivering the best trade-off between mass and stiffness. Its efficiency advantage is robust across both investigated beam lengths and throughout the Pareto frontier. C1, while feasible, is less efficient and should only be adopted in constrained cases. Z1 should generally be avoided due to its poor mass efficiency, whereas Z2 offers a reasonable compromise when Z-type geometries are necessary. These conclusions provide clear guidance for structural engineers seeking to optimize thin-walled beams, demonstrating the value of multi-objective optimization as a decision-making tool in balancing conflicting design criteria.

Acknowledgements

The project was funded by the National Science Centre, Poland allocated on the basis of the decision No. DEC-2021/43/B/ST8/00845 of 2022-05-23 – Contract No. UMO-2021/43/B/ST8/00845.

The paper is developed based on the statutory activity of the Poznań University of Technology (Grant of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland no 0612/SBAD/3640)

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